

Textile Wastewater: High-Impact Zero Liquid Discharge for Sustainable Effluent Treatment

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Abstract:

The textile industry is a vital contributor to India's economy, but it is also one of the largest consumers of water and a significant source of industrial wastewater. Dyeing, finishing, and washing processes release effluents laden with dyes, salts, heavy metals, and other chemicals, contributing to high chemical oxygen demand (COD), biological oxygen demand (BOD), and non-biodegradable pollutants. Conventional wastewater treatment technologies such as reverse osmosis (RO), multiple-effect evaporators (MEE), and advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are effective but highly capital- and energy-intensive, making them unsuitable for small- and medium-scale industries. This paper explores the use of coagulation–flocculation (C–F) as a cost-effective and scalable method to achieve Zero Liquid Discharge (ZLD) in the textile industry. By optimizing coagulant type, dosage, and process conditions, this approach significantly reduces COD and color at a fraction of the cost of advanced methods. A detailed comparison of ZLD technologies demonstrates that C–F is an effective pre-treatment or standalone option, providing an economical solution to wastewater recycling and reuse, supporting both environmental compliance and water conservation.

Keywords: Coagulation–flocculation process, Cost-effective wastewater management, Effluent reuse and recycling, Textile wastewater treatment, Zero Liquid Discharge (ZLD)

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1. Introduction

India's textile industry is one of the largest in the world, contributing substantially to the country's GDP and employment, particularly in states like Gujarat, Tamil Nadu, and Maharashtra. However, its heavy reliance on water and chemical-intensive processes presents severe environmental challenges. Textile manufacturing consumes vast volumes of water, approximately 425 million gallons daily, and generates highly contaminated wastewater containing dyes, salts, heavy metals, alkalis, acids, and other pollutants [1, 2 & 3]. Cotton cultivation, a key raw material source, adds to this water footprint, requiring up to 10,000 liters of water per kilogram [4].

The dyeing and finishing processes alone account for nearly 20% of global industrial water pollution. This wastewater, if untreated, leads to ecological degradation, harming aquatic ecosystems and posing risks to human health. The complexity of textile effluents, characterized by high salinity, alkalinity, and color, makes treatment challenging, requiring innovative and sustainable solutions.

Zero Liquid Discharge (ZLD) has emerged as a promising approach to address these issues, ensuring that no wastewater is discharged into the environment. Importantly, ZLD directly supports the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically Goal 6 (ensuring

access to clean water and sanitation), Goal 12 (fostering responsible production and consumption), Goal 14 (conserving marine ecosystems), and Goal 15 (protecting terrestrial ecosystems by minimizing pollution). However, most ZLD technologies, such as RO, MEE, and membrane filtration, are prohibitively expensive and energy-intensive for small and medium enterprises (SMEs). This research investigates the potential of coagulation–flocculation as a low-cost, high-impact technology for ZLD in the textile sector.[5-10].

2. Textile Industry Wastewater Characteristics

Textile wastewater is highly variable, depending on the type of fabric, dyeing methods, and chemicals used. It typically contains, Dyes and pigments, and Azo dyes, which account for over 50% of dyes used, are persistent, carcinogenic, and resistant to biodegradation. Salts and alkalis: Sodium chloride and sodium sulfate are extensively used during dyeing, leading to high salinity that inhibits biological treatment. Heavy metals: Chromium, copper, and iron compounds are used as mordants and dye fixatives. Other additives: Starch, formaldehyde, surfactants, and various finishing agents. All stages in the textile industry generate heavily contaminated wastewater, as shown in Figure 1.

These pollutants collectively contribute to high COD and BOD levels, color, turbidity, and toxicity, making textile wastewater among the most challenging industrial effluents to treat [11].

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Figure 1: wastewater generation in the textile industry

3. Challenges in Textile Wastewater Treatment

The persistence of dyes and other synthetic chemicals limits the effectiveness of conventional biological treatment methods. High salt concentrations, heavy metals, and toxic compounds further inhibit microbial activity. Advanced treatment technologies like ozonation, Fenton's reagent, and photocatalysis can break down complex molecules but

involve high costs, intensive energy requirements, and specialized infrastructure.

Moreover, small and medium enterprises, which constitute a significant portion of India's textile industry, often lack the capital and space for installing sophisticated wastewater treatment plants. There is, therefore, an urgent need for simple, affordable, and effective treatment solutions [12].

Figure 2: Effects of wastewater from the textile industry

4. Overview of Textile Wastewater Treatment Technologies [13]

To achieve effective treatment and water reuse, industries often employ a combination of physical, chemical, and biological methods. The main approaches include:

- i. **Coagulation–Flocculation (C–F):** A chemical process that uses coagulants such as alum, ferric chloride, or polyaluminum chloride to destabilize particles and dyes, forming flocs that can be removed via sedimentation or filtration. C–F is highly effective for color and COD removal and can reduce treatment costs when optimized.
- ii. **Membrane Filtration:** Ultrafiltration (UF), nanofiltration (NF), and reverse osmosis (RO) separate pollutants based on molecular size. These methods are

effective for desalination and dye removal but are hindered by high costs and membrane fouling.

- iii. **Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs):** Techniques like ozonation and photocatalysis generate hydroxyl radicals to oxidize non-biodegradable compounds. These methods are powerful but energy-intensive.
- iv. **Biological Treatment:** Conventional activated sludge systems are widely used but fail to degrade synthetic dyes effectively. They are best employed as part of a hybrid system.
- v. **Electrocoagulation:** An electrochemical process that destabilizes pollutants using an electric current. While effective, it is energy-intensive and less feasible for small-scale plants.

Table 1: Summary of Wastewater Treatment Methods

Method	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages
Coagulation–Flocculation	Uses chemicals to destabilize and aggregate particles.	Effective at reducing COD and color; simple setup.	Sludge generation; chemical cost.
Membrane Filtration	Uses semi-permeable membranes for separation.	Removes salts and dyes effectively.	High cost; fouling issues.
AOPs	Oxidizes organic pollutants with radicals.	Effective for persistent compounds.	Expensive; energy-intensive.
Biological Treatment	Uses microbes to degrade organics.	Low cost; effective for BOD.	Ineffective for dyes.
Electrocoagulation	Electric current destabilizes pollutants.	Works on various pollutants.	High energy demand.

5. Zero Liquid Discharge (ZLD) Implementation

The Indian textile industry is among the largest consumers of water globally, with dyeing, finishing, and washing processes contributing significantly to both water usage and industrial wastewater generation. It is estimated that the industry consumes over 425 million gallons of water per day, making water sustainability a critical concern, especially in water-stressed regions. Specific water consumption varies by

L/kg for knit composite units. Even upstream, cotton cultivation demands up to 10,000 liters per kilogram, contributing further to the industry's overall water footprint [14].

This extensive water use leads to equally large volumes of wastewater, which often contains dyes, heavy metals (e.g., chromium), alkalis (NaOH), starch, acids, and other hazardous chemicals. Dyeing and finishing processes alone account for approximately 17–20% of the total industrial wastewater. If not adequately treated, this wastewater can contaminate water bodies, posing serious risks to ecosystems and human health [14].

To address these issues, Effluent Treatment Plants (ETPs) are mandated for all textile units under government regulation. However, conventional treatment systems often fall short of achieving complete water reuse. In response, the concept of Zero Liquid Discharge (ZLD) has emerged as a sustainable solution. ZLD aims to eliminate any discharge of liquid waste from industrial premises by recovering, recycling, and reusing the entire wastewater stream. There are some zero liquid discharge (ZLD) Methods in use, such as Reverse Osmosis (RO), Multiple Effect Evaporator (MEE), Membrane Filtration, Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs), Spray Dryer, Constructed Wetlands, etc. These methods are compared in Table 2 [16-19].

5.1 Criteria for Effectiveness Rating (★ system)

Distribution of Water Usage in Textile Production

Figure 3: Textile industry's overall water footprint [15]

process type, ranging from 28 L/kg for denim dyeing to 285

Figure 2: Process flowchart of Yarn Manufacture from Recycled Cotton Fiber

ZLD Method	Mechanism	Effectiveness	Energy Use	Capital Cost	Operating Cost	Suitability
RO	Membrane separation	★★★★☆	High	Very High	High	Low
MEE	Thermal evaporation	★★★★★	Very High	Extremely High	Very High	Low
Membrane Filtration	Size-based separation	★★★★☆	Moderate	High	Moderate	Moderate
AOPs	Oxidation with radicals	★★★★☆	High	High	High	Low
Spray Dryer	Thermal drying	★★★★★	Extremely High	Very High	Very High	Low
Constructed Wetlands	Natural filtration	★★☆☆☆	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate
Coagulation – Flocculation	Particle destabilization	★★★☆☆	Low	Very Low	Very Low	High

The **effectiveness rating** (from ★☆☆☆☆ to ★★★★★) is based on four key performance parameters in textile/dye wastewater treatment:

Pollutant Removal Efficiency

Ability to reduce COD, BOD, color, TDS, and toxic dyes. High efficiency (>90%) earns higher stars.

Water Recovery Rate

The extent to which treated water can be reused in industrial processes.

Higher water recovery (>80%) increases rating.

Robustness & Reliability

Consistency of performance across variable wastewater quality (pH, salinity, dye type). Technologies less prone to failure/fouling rank higher.

Scalability & Industrial Applicability

Suitable for both large and small-scale industries. Adaptability to existing effluent treatment infrastructure.

Star Rating Explanation

- ★☆☆☆☆ – Very low effectiveness (removes <40% pollutants, low water recovery, highly inconsistent).
- ★★☆☆☆ – Limited effectiveness (40–60% removal, suitable only for specific pollutants, poor scalability).
- ★★★☆☆ – Moderate effectiveness (60–75% removal, can handle mixed effluents but with limitations).
- ★★★★☆ – High effectiveness (75–90% removal, reliable under varied conditions, industrially applicable).
- ★★★★★ – Excellent effectiveness (>90% removal, high water recovery, robust and scalable).

So in the **Table of ZLD Methods**, the ★★☆☆☆ rating for **Coagulation–Flocculation** reflects:

Strengths: Good COD and color removal (60–80%), very low cost, easy for SMEs.

Limitations: Does not remove dissolved salts effectively, has a sludge disposal issue, and has lower long-term water recovery than RO or MEE.

5.2 Economic comparison of ZLD methods

Table 3: Typical Cost Ranges for different ZLD methods

Method	Capital Cost (CAPEX)	Operating Cost (OPEX)	Typical Cost per m ³	Remarks
Reverse Osmosis (RO)	\$300–500/m ³ installed capacity	\$0.70–1.00/m ³	\$1.0–1.5	High brine reject, membranes need frequent replacement
Multiple Effect Evaporator (MEE)	\$600–800/m ³ capacity	\$2.0–3.5/m ³	\$3.0–4.5	Very energy-intensive (steam), viable for high-salinity brines
Nanofiltration / UF	\$250–400/m ³ capacity	\$0.50–0.90/m ³	\$0.8–1.2	Good for color and partial COD removal, prone to fouling
Advanced Oxidation (AOPs)	\$200–350/m ³ capacity	\$1.5–2.5/m ³	\$2.0–3.0	High chemical and energy demand, good for recalcitrant dyes
Spray Dryer (brine drying)	\$800–1200/m ³ capacity	\$3.0–4.0/m ³	\$4.0–5.0	Used only as a final ZLD step for concentrated brines
Constructed Wetlands	\$50–100/m ³ capacity	\$0.10–0.30/m ³	\$0.2–0.4	Land-intensive, not suitable for high-strength textile effluents
Coagulation–Flocculation (C–F)	\$50–150/m ³ capacity	\$0.10–0.20/m ³	\$0.2–0.3	Cheapest method, effective for COD/color, but limited for TDS removal

a. Define Cost Categories

Capital Cost (CAPEX): Infrastructure, equipment, installation.

Operating Cost (OPEX): Chemicals, energy, labor, membrane replacement, and sludge handling.

Cost per m³ of Treated Water: A normalized figure for direct comparison across methods.

b. Typical Cost Ranges (from literature & industry reports)

(Values are indicative, vary with plant size, effluent load, and region; all in USD per m³ wastewater treated)

c. Interpretation

Coagulation–Flocculation (C–F) is by far the cheapest option (~\$0.2–0.3/m³) due to low chemical and infrastructure costs.

MEE and Spray Dryers are the most expensive (~\$3–5/m³) and are only used where complete ZLD is mandated.

RO and Membrane Systems fall in the middle but require frequent maintenance and high electricity use.

Combining C–F as a pre-treatment with RO or AOPs significantly reduces total costs by lowering the pollutant load before high-end polishing steps.

All ZLD is typically implemented using energy-intensive and capital-heavy technologies such as Reverse Osmosis (RO), Multiple Effect Evaporators (MEE), membrane filtration, and advanced oxidation processes. These technologies, while effective, are financially out of reach for many small and medium enterprises (SMEs) due to their high cost and space requirements.

6. Materials and Methods

Analytical grade alum, lime, ferric chloride (FeCl₃), and ferrous sulfate (FeSO₄) were sourced from Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (SRL), India. Commercially available anionic (A), cationic (B), and nonionic (C) polymers were obtained from local distributors and used as flocculants. Standard reagents required for COD estimation were freshly

prepared in the laboratory, following the procedures outlined in the American Public Health Association (APHA) guidelines.

Case study: Wastewater treatment with said method was carried out for many dyes and dye intermediate industries around Ahmedabad. One case is discussed here of M/s Varahi Intermediates, G.I.D.C. Naroda, Gujarat, a facility engaged in the production of metaphenylene diamine-4-sulphonic acid (MPDSA). MPDSA serves as a key intermediate in the synthesis of mordant and reactive dyes widely used by textile industries and process houses. The wastewater generated from textile industries using these dyes will have similar characteristics to wastewater generated from Ms Varahi intermediates. The untreated effluent was characterized by a COD of ~32,000 mg/L and a TDS concentration of 566 mg/L.

Jar test experiments were conducted for coagulation–flocculation trials, following standard APHA procedures. Stock solutions of coagulants and flocculants were prepared in distilled water. For each run, 10 mL of coagulant solution was added to 100 mL of wastewater and mixed for 60–70s. This was followed by the addition of 1 mL of flocculant solution with slow mixing (30–40 rpm) and subsequent settling. The clarified supernatant was separated by filtration. For further polishing, 1.0g of activated carbon was added per 100 mL of partially treated water, stirred for 10 min at 50–60 rpm, and filtered to obtain a colorless, clear effluent.

Initially, conventional single-stage trials were performed using one coagulant paired with one flocculant (alum–A/B/C, lime–A/B/C, etc.). Later, combined coagulant approaches were tested to enhance efficiency, particularly lime–alum and lime–FeCl₃ systems, each applied with different flocculants (A/B/C). For all cases, 10% coagulant solutions and 1% flocculant solutions were prepared in distilled water.

7. Results and Discussion

Analyses of COD and TDS were conducted according to the APHA standard methods.

In conventional single-stage treatment with individual coagulants, reductions in TDS were negligible. While COD levels decreased moderately, sludge generation was significant, and overall performance was unsatisfactory. To address this, a two-stage treatment strategy was adopted. This modification led to marked reductions in both COD and TDS.

When coagulants were paired and applied in two stages, a substantial improvement was observed. For example, lime–alum treatment reduced TDS to ~450 ppm with anionic flocculant and 370 ppm with cationic flocculant. However, nonionic flocculants were less effective, failing to reduce TDS below 450 ppm. By contrast, lime–FeCl₃ combinations did not yield appreciable improvements in TDS removal.

COD analysis revealed more promising outcomes. In Stage 1, COD decreased from 32,000 mg/L to ~25,000 mg/L, while Stage 2 further reduced it to ~10,000 mg/L. Among the combinations, lime–FeCl₃ outperformed lime–alum in COD reduction. Subsequent activated carbon treatment polished the effluent to below 50 mg/L COD and <150 mg/L TDS. These final values fall well below statutory discharge limits (200 mg/L COD, 500 mg/L TDS), rendering the water suitable for reuse within the plant. Table 4 shows all results and is compared in Figure 4. Although color intensity decreased after the coagulation–flocculation process, complete decolorization was only achieved following activated carbon adsorption. This highlights the importance of combining physico-chemical treatment with adsorptive polishing for high-strength dye intermediate effluents.

Table 4: Results of experiments

Treatment Method	Flocculant Type	TDS (ppm)	COD (mg/L)	Remarks
Untreated Wastewater	–	545	32,000	Highly colored, turbid
Lime (single coagulant)	Anionic	510	29,000	Minimal TDS reduction, slight COD drop
	Cationic	520	2850	–
	Nonionic	526	28,800	Ineffective
Alum (single coagulant)	Anionic	525	27,000	Some COD removal, weak TDS effect
	Cationic	410	2450	Significant COD reduction
	Nonionic	390	25,000	Best TDS reduction in a single stage
FeCl ₃ (single coagulant)	Anionic	540	28,800	No major effect
	Cationic	542	29,200	–
	Nonionic	538	29,000	–
Lime & Alum (two - stage)	Anionic	450	20,000	Improved reduction
	Cationic	370	1800	Strong TDS + COD reduction
	Nonionic	460	21,000	Less effective
Lime & FeCl ₃ (two-stage)	Anionic	520	17,000	Effective COD reduction
	Cationic	515	15,000	Better COD removal than Lime–Alum
	Nonionic	525	18,500	Weak TDS impact

Figure 4: Comparison of experimental results

Treatment with activated charcoal resulted in a significant reduction in both color and COD and produced clear, colorless water. Final COD levels dropped to 30 mg/L, and in several cases, values were observed to be as low as 10 mg/L. The treated effluent thus became suitable for reuse within the process, eliminating the need for external discharge of water from the plant. In the primary treatment stage, the use of coagulants such as ferric chloride, alum, and polyelectrolytes effectively facilitated the separation of colloidal matter from wastewater. However, this process generated a considerable volume of sludge, which requires safe disposal through a Treatment, Storage, and Disposal Facility (TSDF). All the pollutants removed by the C-F method will be carried away by the sludge generated by it to clean the water.

The use of alternative coagulants, such as pre-hydrolyzed metallic salts, is often more effective than the hydrolyzing metallic salts, such as ferric chloride, aluminum sulfate (alum), and ferric sulfate, which are readily soluble in water. Pre-hydrolyzed coagulants such as poly-aluminum chloride (PACl), polyaluminum ferric chloride (PAFCI), polyferrous sulfate (PFS), and polyferric chloride (PFCI) seem to exhibit better color removal even at low temperatures and may also produce a lower volume of sludge. The effectiveness of PACl products gives more rapid flocculation and stronger flocs compared to alum at an equivalent dosage. This can be attributed to the fact that these coagulants are pre-

neutralized, have a smaller effect on the pH of the water, and so reduce the need for pH adjustment.

Commonly used textile dyes are ionic, mostly anionic, and hence, the cationic polymer can be preferred as it exhibits better dye removal performance, due to its opposite surface charge attraction. Different coagulants affect different degrees of destabilization. The higher the valence of the counter ion, the more its destabilizing effect and the less the dose needed for coagulation. Alum, ferric chloride, and ferric sulfate are the most widely used chemical coagulants with varying dose amounts in textile wastewater treatment.

8. Advantages of Coagulation–Flocculation

- i. Low Capital Investment: Requires only simple tanks and settling chambers.
- ii. Minimal Energy Requirements: No need for high-pressure pumps or thermal units.
- iii. Cost-Effective Chemicals: Readily available coagulants like lime, alum, and PAC.
- iv. Space Efficiency: Ideal for SMEs and decentralized plants.
- v. Integration Capability: Can serve as a pre-treatment for RO or MEE to reduce costs.

9. Government Initiatives and Industry Adoption

Government schemes like the Integrated Processing Development Scheme (IPDS) encourage water conservation through funding support for effluent treatment plants. Many companies are adopting closed-loop systems, digital printing, enzyme-based processes, and organic cotton cultivation to lower their water footprint.

Coagulation–flocculation fits into this ecosystem as a scalable, low-barrier solution.

10. Conclusion

Zero Liquid Discharge is both an environmental and economic necessity for India's textile industry. High-cost ZLD technologies are often inaccessible for SMEs, making it imperative to adopt low-cost yet effective alternatives. This study demonstrates that coagulation–flocculation, when optimized, is a viable, scalable, and economical method for wastewater treatment, reducing COD, color, and other contaminants to levels suitable for reuse. Future research should focus on innovative coagulants, hybrid treatment systems, and sludge minimization to further enhance the sustainability of this approach.

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